

Preparation of carvacrol aldehyde.—A solution of carvacrol (15 g.) in a mixture of chloroform (16 c. c.) and alcohol (50 c. c.) was added drop by drop with constant stirring to a solution of caustic soda (20 g. in 83 c. c. of water) which was kept in a flask fitted with an upright condenser. The reaction was carried at 40° for 10 hours. The alcohol and the excess of chloroform was driven off and the solution made strongly acidic when a deep red oil separated out. The mixture was distilled in steam when the aldehyde separated as a reddish oil in the distillate which was taken up with ether and purified through the bisulphite compound in the usual way. Deep red liquid boiling at 237°; soluble in alcohol and ether, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 74.0; H, 8.01. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.15; H, 7.86 per cent). This is the *ortho*-aldehyde as it is volatile with steam and gives a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The *p*-aldehyde seems not to be formed in this case. The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, crystallises from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 252°. (Found: N, 18.10. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.86 per cent).

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On Ketimine-enamine Compounds.

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In the literature differences of opinion with regard to the mode of behaviour of ketimine-enamine tautomeric compounds in condensation reactions are largely in evidence, where the main issue has been whether the compounds react in their ketimine form (*cf.*, Burns, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1893, ii, 47, 105; Meyer, *Chem. Centr.*, 1908, II, 591), or are active in their enamine phase (Combes and Combes, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1893, iii, 7, 778; Benary, Reiter and Soenderop, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 83). Even phenylcarbimide, a reagent which appears to have little effect upon the different isomers when dissolved in a non-ionising solvent, reacts (*cf.* Behrend and Meyer, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 621) with both forms of the above tautomeric compounds. Consequently they

might be regarded as existing in both the modifications particularly in the liquid state, or in solution in a condition of dynamic equilibrium; when a more complicated problem would be involved in each type of their reactions, the mode of which will depend on the conditions of the reaction, the nature of the reagent, or both.

By applying the general principles of cationotropy (*Annual Reports*, 1927, p. 106) it may be noticed that in the dissociation of the mobile hydrogen atom from the system (I) an electromeric anion (II) is left behind, where the tautomeric electron displacements $\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{N}} = \overset{\curvearrowleft}{\text{C}} - \text{C} \cdot \text{X}$, bring about a redistribution of the negative charge between the nitrogen and carbon atoms, the eliminated cation (hydrogen) having thereby two points of reassociation. Accordingly the changes involved in coming into equilibrium under a particular condition are:

The equilibrium of the system will consequently depend jointly on the relative stability of the two anions (II) and (III), and on that of the covalent linkages by means of which the common cation (hydrogen) associates with each of them.

Now the more electronegative nitrogen atom would have a more powerful attraction for the cation and the consequence would be that the compound would exist mainly in the enamine form (IV) in its equilibrium. Certain physical methods, such as magnetic rotation (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 61, 828) and absorption spectra (Auwers and Susemihl, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1072), that have been so far employed to elucidate the constitution of such compounds, favour the enamine form (IV). On the basis of this assumption the mode of various reactions of the tautomeric compounds of the ketimine-enamine type may be easily considered and an attempt may be made to find out a solution of the problems involved, although the inherent defect of the chemical method of handling equilibrium mixtures cannot but be recognised.

The enhanced activity of the enamine phase was first of all recorded by Beyer (*Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 1662; *cf.* also Knoevenagel, *ibid.*, 1903, **36**, 1280, 2188) who represented the reaction of ketimine-enamine compounds with $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones in the following way:

These condensations are carried out in solution or better by heating the mixture above their fusion point, either condition would favour the enamine phase (*cf.* Auwers and Susemihl, *loc. cit.*). That the enamine form is responsible for this type of condensation is also evident from two negative results previously recorded (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 321) during the condensation of benzal benzoylacetone with ethyl tetrahydroanthranilate and methyl acetylacetone. In their reaction with hydroxymethylene ketones (Basu, *Annalen*, 1934, **514**, 292) too, it is most natural to expect that the ketimine-enamine tautomeric compounds will react in their enamine form with unsaturated ketone, $\text{HO} \cdot \text{CH} : \text{CH} \cdot \text{COR}$, represented by the hydroxymethylene phase of the dicarbonyl compound. That the acetate of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone behaves analogously (Basu, *Annalen*, 1934, **512**, 133) further supports the above hypothesis.

When the compounds are treated with esters in presence of sodium, the products of reaction are always *N*-derivatives (Benary and Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 2161). In these cases the electro-negative nitrogen would attract the more positive cation sodium and the consequence would be a predominance of the enamine form (IV) in the system. Under these circumstances the ester molecule might be drawn towards the unsaturated nitrogen atom whose unsaturation has further been enormously increased by its association with the highly positive sodium atom, and the result of the reaction would be the production of *N*-acyl derivatives. A direct deduction from this idea would be a synthesis of a pyridone derivative (VII) by reacting a tautomeric compound of the type (V) with an ester molecule containing an appropriately situated methylene group, such as in ethyl cyanoacetate. The *N*-acyl derivative (VI), that would be initially

formed, might readily pass into the pyridone derivative (VII) owing to a tendency for the formation of a six-membered ring thus :

The isolation of 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (XV) from the condensation of benzoyl acetonamine with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of sodium is quite in agreement with the above view. Quite a different problem is most likely involved in their reaction with cyanoacetamide, for the above amine gave with cyanoacetamide the isomeric pyridone derivative, 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIV) (Basu, *loc. cit*), the mechanism of this latter reaction being represented by the scheme :

Knoevenagel and Cremer (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 2395), however, represented a similar action between acetyl acetoamine and malonamide in a different way thus :

But as the amine has been obtained from a symmetrical β diketone, their reaction is quite as readily explained by the mechanism:

To have a clear idea on this point, three amines (VIII), (IX) and (X) have been respectively prepared from the unsymmetrical dicarbonyl compounds, benzoylacetone, ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl *cyclohexanone*-2-carboxylate, and digested with malonamide in an oil-bath when the expected condensation products (XI), (XII) and (XIII) were isolated from the corresponding reaction mixture.

Lastly the activity of the tautomeric compounds in their ketimine form in certain cases (in the reaction of diacetonitrile with hydroxylamine hydrochloride as observed by Burns, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1893, *ii*, 47, 105) might be due to the driving back by hydrion (the presence of hydrochloric acid increasing the concentration of hydrion), of the dissociation of the mobile hydrogen of the tautomeric compound in question, with resulting increase in the proportion of the ketimine form (1).

An interesting fact that arises out of this investigation is the directive influence of the carbethoxy group in ethyl cyanoacetate in its reaction with enamine compounds. When, however, instead of the ester cyanoacetamide is made to react with them, the directive influence disappears and the structural reactivity of the conjugated double bonded system as present in the enamine form (IV) of the tautomeric system reasserts itself. An outcome of this work, therefore, is that it provides a method of isolating and distinguishing the different isomers usually obtained in the condensation of 1:3-dicarbonyl compounds either with cyanoacetic ester in presence of ammonia according to Issoglio (*Atti. R. Accad. Sci. Torino*, 1905, 40, 495), or with cyanoacetamide in presence of a basic condensing agent according to Sen-Gupta (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347). For example, benzoylacetone gives with cyanoacetamide a mixture of two pyridone derivatives (XIV) and (XV), the isolation of the latter in its pure form being extremely difficult (*cf.* Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 489); the amido derivative (XVI), on the contrary, gives with cyanoacetamide only the compound (XIV). The other isomer (XV), however, may be obtained by condensing the amido compound with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of sodium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzoylacetoneamine, (VIII) was prepared by the method of Knoevenagel (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2188) and obtained in shining plates, m.p. 143°.

(i) *Action with malonamide*.—An equimolecular mixture of malonamide and benzoylacetoneamine was heated in an oil-bath at 175-80° for about an hour, when the reaction took place with copious evolution of ammonia. The residue was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 286-87°. (Found: N, 12.43. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.28 per cent). The compound is soluble in water, alkali and concentrated acids. On heating with 80% sulphuric acid for about half an hour it gave a product, m.p. 182° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 7.63. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.57 per cent). The hydrolysed product is easily soluble in dilute alkali and gives a reddish colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It was identified as 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2223); accordingly the mother compound would be 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone-3-carbonamide (XI).

(ii) *Action with ethyl cyanoacetate*.—To an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide containing 0.9 g. of sodium, benzoylacetoneamine (6.5 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (4.5 g.) also dissolved in absolute alcohol was added and the mixture was heated under reflux at 110° for about 3 hours. Within half an hour a clear solution was obtained and gradually a solid separated out. After allowing the mixture to remain at the room temperature for 24 hours, water was added to have a clear solution and this on acidification gave a white solid which on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 277°. (Found: N, 13.40. $C_{13}H_{13}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent). The substance is soluble in alkali and concentrated acids from which solutions it is precipitated unchanged on acidification and dilution respectively. On hydrolysis with 80% sulphuric acid the compound gave the known 4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone, m.p. 207°, the m.p. being not depressed when mixed with an authentic sample of the pyridone obtained from the stock. Evidently the mother product was 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (XV).

(iii) *Action with cyanoacetmethylamide*.—An equimolecular mixture of the amine and cyanoacetmethylamide (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 492) when heated at 150° in an oil-bath for more than half an hour gave a product melting indifferently at

252°. It was partly soluble in caustic alkali. The main and insoluble portion separated from alcohol in prismatic needles. m.p. 266° and was found to be 3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIV, $\text{NH}=\text{N}\cdot\text{Me}$) (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 327). (Found: N, 12.67. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 12.50 per cent). The above alkaline solution on acidification gave a small quantity of 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (Issoglio, *loc. cit.*), m.p. 310°, on crystallisation from acetic acid. The isolation of the latter compound indicates that most probably the ammonia set free during the condensation reaction transforms part of cyanoacetmethylamide to cyanoacetamide and it is this latter reagent that is responsible for the production of 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIV).

Ethyl β -aminocrotonate, $\text{Me C}(\text{NH}_2):\text{CH}\cdot\text{COOEt}$ (IX).

(i) *Action with malonamide*.—The condensation was effected as usual by heating an equimolecular mixture of ethyl β -aminocrotonate (Michaelis, *Annalen*, 1909, 366, 337) and malonamide in an oil-bath for more than an hour. The reacted mixture was then acidified with the dilute hydrochloric acid and the solid separated on crystallisation from the boiling water melted at 198° with decomposition. (Found: C, 49.89; H, 4.85; N, 16.52. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires C, 50.0; H, 4.76; N, 16.66 per cent).

It dissolves in sodium carbonate solution with effervescence, is coloured bluish green when warmed with sodium nitrite solution and imparts a reddish violet colouration to an alcoholic ferric chloride solution. On boiling with caustic alkali it evolves ammonia but on heating with fuming hydrochloric acid at 150° for more than 3 hours and on subsequent neutralisation with sodium carbonate, the product yielded a different compound which on crystallisation from water melted at 194°. (Found: N, 11.12. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 11.20 per cent).

This compound is the known 4-methyl-2:6-dioxypyridine and has been previously synthesised by Rogerson and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87 1685), consequently the condensation product would be 4-methyl-6-oxy-2-pyridone-3-carbonamide (XII). This condensation was also brought about by dissolving malonamide (1 mol.) and the aminocrotonate (1 mol.) in dilute alcohol with the addition of a few c.c. of piperidine. The solution was left at the room temperature. After 4 days it was concentrated and acidified when the above carbonamide derivative separated out.

Ethyl tetrahydroanthranilate (X).—The anthranilate derivative was prepared by passing ammonia to ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate* according to Dieckmann (*Annalen*, 1901, 317, 27) and was obtained in shining plates, m.p. 74°. Ethyl tetrahydroanthranilate (8.45 g.) and malonamide (5.1 g.) were intimately mixed and the mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 190° for several hours. The mass was then treated with dilute hydrochloric acid when a very small quantity of a solid was isolated. On crystallisation from dilute acetic acid it melted at 183-84°. (Found: N, 13.70. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.46 per cent).

The compound readily dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence, imparts a bluish violet colouration to alcoholic ferric chloride and gives a deep yellow colour with sodium nitrite solution. On hydrolysis with fuming hydrochloric acid as usual it gave a product which on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 205° and was found to be identical with 1:3-dioxy-5:6:7:8-tetrahydroisoquinoline (Basu, *loc. cit.*) The initial condensation product necessarily is 1-oxy-3-keto-2:3:5:6:7:8-hexahydroisoquinoline-4-carbonamide (XIII). A better yield of the condensation product was obtained by condensing ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate* with malonamide (1:1) in dilute alcoholic solution in presence of piperidine.

Benzoylacetone methylamine $Me C(NH Me) : CH \cdot CO \cdot Ph$.—This methylamine derivative was obtained by treating benzoylacetone with 33 % solution of methylamine according to Beyer (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1669).

(i) *Action with ethyl cyanoacetate*.—An alcoholic solution of benzoylacetone methylamine (7.0 g.) was added to a solution of sodium ethoxide containing about 0.9 g. of sodium. To this ethyl cyanoacetate (4.5 g.) was then added and the mixture was heated under reflux at 110° for more than 5 hours. On careful acidification and dilution with water the mixture gave unchanged benzoylacetone methylamine indicating thereby that no reaction had taken place in this case as there was no chance for the formation of an intermediate sodium salt of the type (VI).

(ii) *Action with cyanoacetamide*.—An intimate mixture of the methyl amide and cyanoacetamide in molecular quantities was heated together in an oil-bath at 125° for about half an hour, when the usual reaction took place with copious evolution of ammoniacal vapour. The major portion of the condensation product was found to be soluble in alkali and from the alkaline solution a compound was isolated

which on recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid melted at 310° . This was found to be 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone already referred to. (Found: N, 13.33. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent).

The insoluble product was crystallised from alcohol when it melted at 266° , the m. p. being not depressed when admixed with the compound 3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone previously obtained by reacting benzoylacetoneamine with cyanoacetmethylamide.

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Dimercapthiothiazole as an Analytical Reagent.

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In a note published previously (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 403) by one of us (J.G.) reference was made to the use of

dimercapthiothiazole or thiothiazole-1:4-dithiol $\begin{array}{c} \text{N} \text{---} \text{N} \\ \parallel \quad \quad \parallel \\ \text{HS} \cdot \text{C} \quad \quad \text{C} \cdot \text{SH} \\ \quad \quad \quad \text{S} \end{array}$ as a

very convenient reagent for the estimation of copper, lead and bismuth, and for their separation from the metals of the II B group and the rest of the analytical groups (*e.g.*, As, Sb, Sn, Mo, Fe, Zn, etc.). Mention was also made of its usefulness as a qualitative micro-reagent for Cu and Bi.

The substance behaves as a weak acid like H_2S , the hydrogen atoms of the sulphydryl groups being replaceable by metals under suitable conditions. It gives characteristic coloured precipitates with most of the elements of the H_2S -group of the analytical table. The precipitates obtained in most of these cases were, however, of variable composition and could not, therefore, be directly weighed, but they settled readily and were easily separated by filtration.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the reagent.—Thiothiazole-1:4-dithiol was most conveniently prepared according to the methods described by